

Architectural Design for Modern House: Display of AI-Powered Digital Twin Systems

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Suggested Citation

Ahmad, T., Babar, A., Asif, S.H., Hamza, A., Bilal, M., Rehman, A., & Ejaz, M.M. (2024). Architectural Design for Modern House: Display of AI-Powered Digital Twin Systems. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 480-491.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).42](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).42)

Abstract:

This study investigates the advancement and utilization of AI-driven digital twin (DT) systems, emphasizing their incorporation with virtual reality (VR) and 3D technologies for the real-time monitoring and optimization of physical assets. A DT is a virtual depiction of a physical asset, facilitated by data and simulations, that provides significant capabilities for prediction, monitoring, and decision-making. This study introduces the modern technologies methods, which examines the role of intelligent building design elements like multi-layout activities and AI simulation model-derived functions in DT-based smart building systems. This study utilizes a modern house to illustrate the application of DT across many capacity tiers,

underpinned by data gathered from an array of sensors within the dwelling. These smart models can be visualized and engaged with in a VR environment, offering an immersive platform for users to examine and modify the virtual house.

Keywords: *modern house, smart building design, AI, digital twin, 3D modeling, virtual reality, building physics, urban planning.*

Introduction

Background

The notion of digital twin (DT) has garnered considerable attention in recent decades, starting in aerospace engineering and then proliferating across diverse sectors including manufacturing, urban planning, healthcare, and, more recently, smart buildings (Niaz, et al., 2022; Shoukat, et al., 2022). The DT function as real-time virtual representations of physical assets, enabled by sophisticated sensor data, simulations, and communication technology. Initially, the DT were implemented to enhance the efficiency and oversight of industrial machinery and manufacturing operations. NASA is frequently acknowledged for its pioneering role in this technology during the initial phases of space exploration, especially in the remote management of spacecraft systems (Niaz, et al., 2021).

Over time, the function of the DT has progressed from basic data-driven monitoring systems to advanced AI-powered instruments capable of predictive analysis and autonomous decision-making. Through the integration of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI), DT can now analyze data to provide actionable insights, thereby improving the management of intricate physical systems with more efficiency (Rani, et al., 2024). The architectural field, especially in smart building design, is progressively gaining advantages from this technological transformation. Structures utilizing DT can enhance energy efficiency, elevate occupant comfort, and forecast maintenance needs through real-time sensor data analysis (Manzoor, Othman, & Pomares, 2021).

DT in architecture utilize computer methods including parametric links, self-organizing algorithms, and AI to generate dynamic, real-time digital representations of physical structures (Naji, et al., 2024). DT utilize data from sensors

integrated into building infrastructure to represent the current condition of the physical structure and forecast future alterations through AI-driven insights. Advancements in deep learning, including GANs, VAEs, and CNNs, enable the autonomous production of architectural components such as floor plans, interiors, and facades, allowing architects to visualize and simulate building performance in virtual settings (Wang, et al., 2024).

Shortages

Notwithstanding the potential of DT, numerous hurdles and research deficiencies persist in their use within contemporary residential and smart city contexts. A significant issue is the absence of standardized frameworks for assessing the maturity and DT systems across many areas. Current implementations of DT exhibit considerable variability in functionality, from simple visual representations to intricate, AI-driven predictive models (Di Stefano, Ruta, & Masera, 2023; Zhang, et al., 2021). This discrepancy impedes the widespread use of DT in architectural and urban applications, where thorough data modelling and decision-making are essential.

The amalgamation of DT with virtual reality (VR) and 3D modelling technology remains inadequately investigated (Shoukat, et al., 2024). Although virtual reality offers the possibility of immersive, real-time engagement with virtual surroundings, its incorporation into DT systems within architecture remains nascent. There is a paucity of study about the enhancement of interaction and usability of DT in smart homes and urban environments using VR and 3D modelling.

A significant deficiency is the insufficient application of generative AI models in urban DT. Although generative AI models such as generative adversarial networks, variational autoencoders, and generative pre-trained transformers have exhibited significant success

in content generation, their utilization in smart city planning and DT systems is predominantly underexplored. These models possess the capacity to independently create design scenarios, anticipate urban planning obstacles, and enhance energy, transportation, and infrastructure systems; however, further study is required to effectively utilize this potential.

Novelties

This study fills existing gaps by introducing a novel paradigm for classifying and assessing DT systems according to their competence levels, from independent models to fully autonomous systems. The notion of "modern house" provides a uniform framework for comprehending and executing DT in smart buildings, applicable across several sectors like energy optimization, security management, and occupant comfort (Shoukat, et al., 2024).

This research innovatively integrates DT with VR and 3D technologies in architecture, utilizing a contemporary house as a case study. The intelligent residence is outfitted with a multitude of sensors that incessantly gather data on temperature, humidity, energy consumption, and various environmental parameters. This data integrates with the DT system, facilitating real-time monitoring, forecasting, and enhancement of the physical house's performance (Himeur, et al., 2023). This research uniquely employs VR to interact with and manage the digital doppelganger, offering consumers an immersive experience that connects physical and virtual settings.

This study examines the possibility of generative AI models in creating urban DT. This research illustrates how advanced machine learning algorithms enable AI to autonomously create urban design scenarios, optimize building configurations, and forecast future trends in urban development. This signifies a substantial advancement in smart city design, providing a scalable and intelligent approach to manage intricate urban systems.

Contributions

- This research offers significant contributions to the domain of DT, especially in relation to contemporary residential architecture and urban planning.
- The "modern house" concept is a significant addition that classifies DT according to their functionality. This framework offers a standardized methodology for assessing and executing DT across diverse businesses, facilitating the evaluation of their potential and constraints.
- The study illustrates how the combination of VR and 3D modelling might augment the efficacy and user engagement of DT systems.
- This research expands the utilization of DT inside urban settings, demonstrating how generative AI models may autonomously create design scenarios and enhance urban systems.

This study facilitates user immersion in a virtual house and real-time interaction with a DT, thereby bridging the divide between physical and virtual surroundings and providing an innovative approach to monitoring and optimizing smart homes. Sensor data is always gathered, analyzed, and integrated into the DT system, facilitating predictive maintenance, energy efficiency, and enhanced occupant comfort. This method signifies a substantial progression in smart building design, providing a more sophisticated and automated means of controlling physical assets. The novel abstract framework (as shown in Figure 1) illustrates an interconnected ecosystem derived from the analysis and synthesis of the theoretical and practical foundations driving the convergence of AI, artificial intelligence of things, DT, data-driven urban planning, and environmental sustainability in sustainable modern house. This interconnection creates a robust framework for promoting sustainable smart home.

Figure 1. A New Developed Approach for Data-Driven Environmental Planning in Sustainable Modern House

Method

DT in Architectural Design

DT model can be parametrically adjusted to investigate various design possibilities, according to user-specified constraints including energy efficiency, space utilization, and occupant comfort. Techniques such as Graph2Plan facilitate user-tailored layouts, while optimization algorithms provide high-performance, cost-efficient solutions that emphasize structural, bioclimatic, and lighting factors. Consequently, DT improve the lifecycle

management of buildings by providing predictive maintenance, sustainability insights, and an interactive platform for users to evaluate design modifications in relation to environmental conditions, ultimately resulting in more resilient and adaptive architectural solutions. To successfully integrate generative AI applications within urban DT—typically deployed on web platforms, cyberinfrastructures, and cloud services to enhance modern house functions—we propose several technical strategies. These approaches aim to improve scalability, performance, and accuracy (as shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2. Technical Strategies for DT Integration

The following method is used to employing DT in the planning and maintenance of an architectural project. This approach emphasizes the integration of real-time data gathering, analysis, and optimization to enhance building performance and design flexibility.

- Deploy sensors in critical spots across the facility to assess essential metrics.
- Incorporate sensors into a centralized IoT infrastructure to provide uninterrupted data transmission.
- Initiate the DT model by delineating the building's geometry, materials, and systems through architectural BIM (Building Information Modelling) data.
- Create a three-dimensional model that accurately represents the geometry, materials, and systems of the physical structure.
- Establish parameters for essential components such as HVAC, lighting, and structural loads.
- Train AI models using historical and real-time data to identify patterns and forecast behaviors across various circumstances.
- Establish cloud-based data storage for the real-time collection of sensor data.
- Utilize APIs to connect the DT with real-time data inputs, thereby updating the virtual model to accurately represent alterations in the building environment.
- Continuously enhance the AI models with new data to optimize predictions and decision-making.
- Conduct simulations for several scenarios, including occupancy surges, severe weather events, or equipment malfunctions.
- Utilize GANs and CNNs to model scenarios for resource optimization, such as energy use and HVAC modifications.

- Implement multi-objective optimization to equilibrate elements such as energy efficiency, occupant comfort, and operational expenses.
- Employ AI models to evaluate sensor data and deliver feedback for immediate control (e.g., modifying HVAC settings according to occupancy or enhancing lighting for energy efficiency).
- Revise the DT to reflect any modifications implemented in the actual environment.
- Equip plant managers with insights via an intuitive interface to modify operating settings.
- Evaluate the simulated performance results against empirical data to confirm the accuracy of the DT.
- Enhance AI models as needed to integrate supplementary variables or augment forecasting precision.
- Employ data analytics to track key performance indicators, such as energy consumption, equipment uptime, and space utilization, for further optimizations.

Utilizing the DT methodology enables architects and facility managers to make data-informed decisions, thereby decreasing operational expenses and improving building sustainability while adjusting the design to changing requirements and environmental factors.

DT for Urban Planning

DT oriented urban planning is advanced virtual model of cities that utilize real-time data and simulations to enhance urban planning and administration, reflecting the interactions among diverse urban subsystems from an integrated sociotechnical perspective (Schrotter, & Hürzeler, 2020). Historically, urban planners and academics have utilized urban DT as vital data-driven instruments to visualize and analyze complex urban dynamics, perform predictive evaluations, enhance decision-making, and allocate resources effectively (Al-Sehrawy,

Kumar, & Watson, 2021). Moreover, computerized house reproductions have often functioned as experimental platforms for evaluating theoretical planning scenarios and urban designs, including land use, zoning, and street configurations. These digital technologies facilitate the development of urban settings that are resilient, sustainable, efficient, human-centric, and habitable.

Study in urban planning has highlighted the capability of AI models to generate realistic, high-dimensional data and hypothetical planning scenarios derived from historical data, facilitating the simulation of intricate urban dynamics and processes, thus enhancing urban analysis. AI enhances the analytical capabilities of DT by producing synthetic data and simulating diverse situations, such as urban growth patterns, demographic changes, and city configurations. This section delineates the core functionalities of urban DT in urban planning, organized into subsections. It additionally examines exemplary AI applications in urban planning that correspond with the data-driven characteristics of urban DT, specifically tailored to facilitate critical urban planning activities.

1. Implement IoT sensors and employ satellite images throughout urban infrastructure to gather ongoing data on traffic, pollution levels, energy usage, and additional metrics.
2. Consolidate this data in a centralized cloud database to guarantee its accessibility and currency.
3. Construct a fundamental 3D model utilizing GIS data and integrate real-time data streams to depict an accurate virtual city twin.
4. Utilize AI models to generate simulations for various urban planning scenarios, like heightened population density, novel public transportation routes, or severe weather occurrences.
5. Generate synthetic data informed by historical trends to replicate demographic changes, urban growth, and infrastructure utilization.
6. Evaluate these scenarios to assess potential effects on the city's infrastructure,

assisting planners in optimizing resource allocation, design, and sustainability.

7. Employ predictive models to forecast challenges such as traffic congestion, pollution levels, or energy consumption, facilitating proactive management.
8. Develop dashboards that illustrate real-time urban dynamics and predictive results, equipping city planners with insights for prompt, data-driven decision-making.
9. Regularly refine the predictive models of the DT utilizing the most recent data to enhance precision.
10. Create an interactive interface enabling stakeholders to examine real-time data, simulations, and potential planning results.
11. Enable scenario testing by permitting users to alter variables (e.g., population density, land use) and promptly visualize the effects on the virtual city.
12. Utilize VR or AR technology to develop immersive experiences, offering stakeholders a concrete understanding of how modifications may affect urban environments.
13. Implement ongoing data streams from IoT devices and public records to ensure the twin's precision in real time.
14. Utilize feedback from scenario testing and actual results to revise the DT and optimize AI models, guaranteeing continuous enhancement.
15. Consistently evaluate the performance of predictive models, retraining as required to adjust to evolving urban patterns and ensure optimal accuracy in planning forecasts.

This approach enables urban planners to make informed decisions based on real-time insights and scenario analysis, facilitating the creation of resilient, sustainable, and efficiently designed urban environments. The incorporation of AI improves DT capabilities by providing realistic and customizable solutions designed to meet the specific needs and problems of each city.

Modern House Model

The utilization of VR hardware to depict a virtual environment augments the visualization

of a DT asset, rendering it more realistic and lifelike. The 3D CAD model of the house was generated using Autodesk Revit software, derived from the 2D floor plans (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Arrangement of All Sensors and Devices Configured for the Project in 2D Floor Layout of a Modern House. All Sensors are Distinguished by Their Labels and Colors, Including Temperature, Proximity, Humidity, Water Detection, and Light Sensors

The three stories were superimposed, with doors and windows precisely positioned. Each surface of the house was labelled and textured to differentiate its many components. This labelling guaranteed that components could be precisely recognized at a subsequent stage if required. The scenario was created with Autodesk 3DS Max and transformed into a format suitable for the Unity3D. Visual textures refer to the perception and interpretation of surface details, including color, shape, size, and density. In 3D rendering software, textures may incorporate effects such as lighting, reflections, and shadows, along with material qualities to enhance realism. A comprehensive 3D model of the house was created using industry-standard technologies and processes to guarantee accuracy and improved visualization of the DT technology.

The project commenced with the transformation of the 2D floor plans, illustrated in Figure 2, into a 3D model. The Autodesk Revit software was utilized to create a 3D model of the house, directly based on the 2D

architectural plans. The Revit platform is ideally suited for this purpose because of its proficiency in BIM (Adeel, et al., 2023), enabling precise architectural representations. Revit's functionalities facilitated the precise placement of essential elements such as walls, doors, and windows throughout the three levels of the residence, guaranteeing architectural fidelity in the 3D rendering procedure.

At this stage, particular emphasis was placed on the accuracy of geometric characteristics, measurements, and spatial configurations. All structural components, including walls, floors, ceilings, windows, and doors, were constructed according to the precise measurements outlined in the 2D drawings. The three narratives were overlapped, guaranteeing flawless synchronization among the levels. This accuracy guaranteed that the model accurately represented the actual layout of the house.

Labelling

Upon completion of the 3D model, surfaces were designated and allocated suitable textures. All surfaces, encompassing walls, floors, and ceilings, were designated with labels to guarantee that distinct components could be easily identified in subsequent phases of the project. Texturing is essential for enhancing the visual realism of the 3D model. The labelling guaranteed that these components could be identified at any later time if required for sensor integration or VR rendering modifications.

Autodesk 3DS Max was utilized to implement these textures and surface features. Visual textures encompassed elements such as color, material type (e.g., wood, concrete, metal), dimensions, form, and density, enhancing the virtual house's visual fidelity to its actual equivalent. These textures also augmented the sense of various surfaces, incorporating lighting effects, reflections, and shadows to replicate real-world materials and environmental circumstances.

VR Integration

After constructing the model and configuring the sensors, the subsequent phase entailed prepping the model for VR integration. Autodesk 3DS Max was utilized to augment the 3D model with intricate effects, including lighting and shadows, essential for constructing a believable VR experience. Upon completion, the model was exported in a format compatible with Unity3D, a framework extensively utilized for real-time 3D content creation and immersive virtual reality experiences.

In Unity3D, the 3D model was converted into an interactive environment (Shoukat, et al., 2022). The VR technology enabled users to immerse themselves in the virtual residence, interacting with the DT in real time. Utilizing VR gear, users may engage with the virtual house, operate its sensors, and see real-time data outputs. Changes in environmental variables, such as temperature or humidity, were represented in the virtual model, reflecting the behavior of the physical dwelling.

In the concluding phase, the DT system was completely connected with VR gear, facilitating real-time interaction between the virtual and physical models. Users could traverse the virtual house and interact with its elements. The system processed the ambient data gathered by the sensors and presented real-time updates in the VR model. This real-time interaction enabled users to remotely experience the house's circumstances and modify characteristics such as lighting or climate control via VR, offering a practical platform for monitoring the physical house's performance.

The creation of the 3D model of the house encompassed multiple phases, including floor plan extraction, 3D CAD modelling, and VR integration. The utilization of advanced tools like Autodesk Revit, Autodesk 3DS Max, and Unity3D facilitated the development of a precise, intricate, and immersive DT system. The addition of real-time sensor data significantly improved the model's usefulness, providing users with an interactive platform for managing and optimizing modern home performance.

Results

Imagine a separate DT of a house that helps a buyer make informed decisions and customize their home. With digitalization in mind, advanced sensors and controllers provide real-time data on indoor air quality, water leaks, door and occupancy status, security, and weather conditions. The homeowner can monitor the house remotely or gain detailed indoor insights when at home. This descriptive DT uses real-time sensor data to give an updated view of the house's status (shown in Figure 4).

Raw data is displayed for easy interpretation, like weather patterns and indoor metrics such as CO₂, humidity, and temperature. The DT database stores these updates, reflecting the house's latest state, such as tracking selected items like a painting or inventory levels, using advanced object detection and classification for detailed monitoring.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Data from the Residual Sensors and Additional Objects, Acquired through a VR Interface, where, (a)Virtual Living Room, and (b) Real Living Room

Discussion

The homeowner possesses extensive high-quality sensor data from both past and present, yet seeks to forecast the future condition of the property to optimize energy use (O'Regan, et al., 2022). They are also interested in comprehending possible alterations, such as the accessibility of natural sunlight resulting from adjacent projects, such as a new high-rise structure.

A predictive model pipeline can be utilized to infer absent temperature data from eight sensors when only the fireplace sensor is operational. This method facilitates ongoing temperature monitoring despite potential sensor failures.

Upon establishing the future temperature profile for the fireplace, this information can be utilized to estimate temperatures at additional sensor locations. The weighted averaging ensemble model's projections for these places exhibit significant concordance with the actual measured temperatures. Ultimately, these point values are converted into contour plots and depicted on the floor surface, offering a lucid picture of temperature distribution within the house.

Limitations

Despite the development of multiple DT applications to tackle difficulties in various sectors of smart cities, significant limitations remain. These challenges frequently stem from the constraints of DT models from both data science and computational viewpoints (Duan, Edwards, & Dwivedi, 2019), in addition to socio-ethical concerns associated with the integration of AI and DT (Filipenko, et al., 2024). We classify these challenges according to their nature in the subsequent subsections and offer a comprehensive analysis of each challenge, along with possible solutions.

Data Science

The data science challenges associated with AI applications pertain to the substantial computational resource requirements for training, deploying, and maintaining these models, encompassing high processing power, extensive memory, and significant energy consumption, which can affect both cost and environmental sustainability (Wang, et al., 2023).

Ethical and Social

Construction Urban DT and modern house encompass several sociotechnical elements that integrate both social and technical features of

these technologies. From a social standpoint, these dimensions encompass governance and policy, ethical considerations, social equality, and cultural and behavioral transformations. In these applications, AI models provide considerable ethical and societal difficulties, particularly regarding prejudice and fairness, as emphasized by Ferrara, (2023). Furthermore, these methods elicit apprehensions regarding openness and accountability.

Others

The study's minor limitations consist of a limited sample size, a restricted number of metrics analyzed, and a small quantity of studied locations. The study underscores the necessity for additional research into the role of AI-driven simulation models and their integration with DT in intelligent building design. A reference model for developing creative architectural design concepts utilizing AI simulation models in conjunction with a DT may serve as a suitable tool for future research. This reference model (architecture), encompassing a standardized vocabulary, reusable designs, and industry best practices, may facilitate the development of diverse applications. It encompasses the frame of reference, interoperability, mergers, acquisitions, outsourcing, benchmarking, and regulatory compliance.

Conclusion

The amalgamation of urban DT with AI models offers a revolutionary methodology for urban planning, empowering cities to address intricate planning dilemmas through a data-driven, predictive, and adaptive framework. DT simulate hypothetical situations, including urban expansion, infrastructure utilization, and environmental effects, so equipping planners with critical foresight to make informed decisions that optimize resources, bolster resilience, and elevate urban living standards. With the rapid acceleration of urbanization and increasing demands on cities, the implementation of AI-driven DT presents a formidable approach for urban areas to develop into sustainable and habitable environments,

thereby changing conventional urban planning into a more resilient and adaptive discipline. This study illustrates the possibility of combining AI-driven DT systems with VR and 3D modelling for improved real-time monitoring and optimization of contemporary residential assets. The study demonstrates the efficacy of DT technology by constructing a comprehensive virtual model of a physical house, equipped with operational sensors for temperature, humidity, lighting, and water detection, thereby illustrating its capability to capture intricate real-world data and convert it into actionable insights. This immersive environment, created with tools like as Autodesk Revit, 3DS Max, and Unity, allows users to engage with and modify the virtual model, enhancing their comprehension of the house's performance under diverse circumstances and competence levels. This research indicates that DT systems possess substantial applicability beyond residential environments, extending to modern house development, where urban subsystems (e.g., transportation, energy, water) can gain from intelligent, autonomous control. Future study should investigate more sophisticated AI models and improved simulations to augment DT functionalities, rendering them more versatile for a broader spectrum of physical assets and operational difficulties. These developments position DT to revolutionize our perception, interaction, and management of physical areas, hence facilitating smarter and more sustainable living situations.

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